

Effectiveness of Internal Branding on Employees to Enhance the Brand Value: An Empirical Study with a focus on Engineering SMEs of Pune

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Keywords: Internal Branding Education, Employees, Brand Ambassador, Engineering SMEs, Brand Value

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Introduction

A company's strong Brand is a valuable asset, but so are its passionate employees. Internal branding education is a business strategy tool to empower and inspire employees to "live" the brand promise rather than just uphold it. The term "brand ambassadorship" describes the level of brand advocacy that employees exhibit or how much they behave as if they are the Brand Ambassadors of the company.

Any business must create a distinct and compelling brand since it is what consumers recall and is drawn to. The relationship between a brand and its employees is vital in how it is presented and how people perceive the Brand. For years, branding has been used to influence how customers view businesses. Internal branding is essential in the digital age because businesses and employees are each other's online brand extensions. Internal branding education allows employees to speak for the entire Brand, including its identity, values, positioning, available products or services, target market, etc. (Figure 1). Internal branding allows them to serve as brand ambassadors, helping to develop desired brand positioning and disseminate the right brand image in the marketplace. An internal branding plan motivates employees to promote and strengthen the Brand.

Figure 1: Internal Branding: The Key to Brand Success

Source: Achim Wirtz (March 27, 2014). Internal Branding: The Key to Brand Success.

<http://hrbranding.org/internal-branding-achim-wirtz/>

1) The Purpose of the Research

- a. This study aims to investigate how employees view their company's Brand concerning their roles and responsibilities and to identify the effectiveness of internal branding in enhancing Brand value by becoming the brand ambassador. From this perspective, the study's main objectives are:
 - To study the aspects on which employees of Engineering SMEs (Small and Medium-sized Enterprises) get training for internal branding.
 - To understand whether Engineering SMEs make sufficient efforts for internal branding education to make their employees the internal Brand Ambassadors
 - To know what factors employees consider vital for delivering their organization's brand promise by becoming brand ambassadors.
- b. With a focus on the above-stated objectives, we address the research question as follows; **"Does the effect of internal branding education on the employees enhance the brand value in Engineering SMEs in Pune city?"**

2) Research Background

This study focuses on the various facets of internal branding and how it affects employees' Motivation. The study has focused on independent variables, i.e., Leadership, Work culture, Motivation, and Internal training. This study aims to determine how much understanding employees possess about the aspects like Brand values, Brand commitment, Brand promise, Products or Service offerings, etc.

3) The Research Design and Method

The research design is based on Quantitative Research. The data collected for this investigation is organized using an empirical research style. The primary data were collected from 150 respondents via convenience sampling. A well-structured survey questionnaire was distributed via email to collect the primary data. Various books, articles, journals, and websites are used to gather secondary data. A questionnaire based on the Likert scale is used.

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis was formed for the study;

H0: "Internal Branding does not significantly impact employees in enhancing the brand value by becoming a Brand Ambassador."

H1: "Internal Branding does have a significant impact on employees in enhancing the brand value by becoming a Brand Ambassador."

Statistical techniques

Statistical tools, including percentages, and tabular and graphical methods, are used to analyze the data. The regression analysis and ANOVA are used to evaluate the hypothesis. The information is gathered, examined, and Pie charts and Bar charts are used to display and present the data.

4) The main results

Testing of Hypothesis

The relationship between the dependent and independent variables was investigated using multivariate regression analysis, which was also utilized to evaluate the study hypothesis. The study's results showed a positive relationship between the dependent variable (enhancing the brand value by acting as a brand ambassador) and the independent variables (Leadership, Work culture, Motivation, and Internal training). The regression model's results are as follows:

Table 1: Table showing Linear Multivariate Regression Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.050 ^a	0.003	-0.004	8.27856

Predictors: (Constant), VAR (leadership, work culture, Motivation, and internal training)

Dependent variable (a): VAR (enhancing the brand value by becoming the brand ambassador)

Interpretation

In Table 1, it is revealed that the multiple correlation coefficient (R) is 0.050, and the coefficient of determination (R Square) is 0.003. The model explains 0.3% of the variation in the dependent variable. The standard error of the estimate is 8.27856, showing actual scores of enhancing brand value. The significant value of internal branding education variables is 0.000, which is less than 0.05, and R has a determined positive value, indicating a strong and distinct correlation between the dependent variable of improving the brand value proving the validity of the alternative hypothesis.

Table 2: ANOVA Table

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	581.996	2	290.998	0.597	.00552 ^b

Residual	74112.675	152	487.583		
Total	74694.671	154			

- a. Dependent Variable: VAR (enhancing the brand value by becoming the brand ambassador)
b. Predictors: (Constant), VAR (leadership, work culture, Motivation, and internal training)

Interpretation

In Table 2, it is revealed that the overall model is significantly helpful in enhancing the brand value by becoming the brand ambassador, $F(2, 152) = 0.597$, Where $p < .05$. **Therefore, it is inferred that internal branding education variables significantly impact brand value by becoming the brand ambassador.**

Summary of the Results

Employees who have received internal branding education help their companies build stronger brands. The survey indicates that the employees feel that their organization has friendly and supportive work environments and progressive leadership and management.

Table 3:

Interpretation

As represented in Table 3, the majority of 28% and 26% of the respondents, respectively, believed that brand development initiatives and external brand-building events are the aspects for which internal communication and engagement happen in their company within the inter-department by the senior management teams. 23% of the respondents considered that company growth is the aspect for which internal communication and engagement happen in their company. Whereas 13% and 10% agreed that customer feedback and employee views & suggestions, respectively, are the aspects for which internal communication and engagement happen in their company within the inter-department by the senior management teams.

Table 4:

Interpretation

As shown in Table 4, 27% of the respondents believed that the internal branding strategy their company applies for expressing to employees how much company management values them. 23% of the respondents thought as a part of the internal training process, followed by 21% who felt to establish transparency within the cross-sectional groups. 18% of them agreed that the strategy is a part of internal communication and engagement. Only 11% said that the strategy is to encourage content creation across the team.

Table 5:

The Figure shows Employee's Objectives as a Brand Ambassador of the Company

Interpretation

Figure 4 reveals that the highest 34% of the respondents agreed that their objective as a brand ambassador of the company is to build the organization's reputation, which is consistent with the brand promise. 28% of the respondents approved that their objective is to form a perception of a strong, distinct, and cohesive brand presence in the focused markets. 23% of the respondents established that their objective as brand ambassadors is to promote the company's

Brand and product to their network, and 15% of the respondents feel that they aim to deliver a consistent customer experience.

5) The significant theoretical and managerial implications

Utilizing internal branding education strategies and internalizing brand attitudes can help organizations increase employee retention. These initiatives are not simply the responsibility of brand managers but also a shared obligation of all employees. The findings showed that implementing internal branding education has a favourable impact on enhancing brand value, which favourably affects brand attitudes, such as brand commitment and brand identification. These attitudes, in turn, have a favourable impact on employee retention.

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